

Adsorption of brilliant green dye from aqueous solution by banana pseudo-stem fibers

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Abstract : In the present work, banana pseudo-stem fiber was used as a biosorbent to adsorb toxic brilliant green dye from aqueous solution. The material was characterized to (i) determine existence of functional groups using Fourier transform infrared (FT-IR) spectroscopy, (ii) analyze morphology using scanning electron microscope (SEM) and (iii) measure crystallinity using X-ray diffractometer (XRD). Batch experiments were performed to observe the effect of pH, contact time, stirring speed, initial dye concentration, adsorbent dose and temperature on the adsorption. The adsorption process followed pseudo-second order kinetics and intra-particle diffusion model. Equilibrium data were fitted to Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm model. The negative values of Gibb's free energy change (ΔG°) show the process is spontaneous. The positive values of enthalpy change (ΔH°) indicate that the process is endothermic. The positive values of entropy change (ΔS°) show increased randomness at the solid/solution interface.

Keywords : Adsorption, banana pseudo-stem fibers, brilliant green, isotherm, thermodynamics.

Introduction

Dyes are widely used in textile, leather, paper, plastic and other industries. Effluents of these industries containing various dyes and pigments are discharged to natural water bodies which pollute the water and consequently cause harm to human and other living organism. Many dyes and pigments have toxic as well as carcinogenic, mutagenic and teratogenic effects¹. Dyes in these effluents are difficult to remove by biological oxidation because the wastewater is influenced by fluctuating pH with a large load of suspended solids and COD, therefore, they require a tertiary treatment². To achieve a high degree of dye removal from wastewater sometimes it is necessary to integrate biological, chemical and physical processes such as coagulation, ultra-filtration, electro-chemical adsorption and photo-oxidation³. Physical adsorption techniques are considered as the preferred means to separate a wide range of chemical compounds^{4,5}. Adsorption of dyes on activated carbon is a common practice but its higher production cost and regeneration difficulty prohibits its frequent use⁶. Consequently a number of low cost adsorbents have been used for the treatment of coloured effluents at different operating conditions with different degree of success⁷. The agricultural wastes, which

have been used for the removal of brilliant green dye include neem leaf powder⁸, bagasse fly ash⁹, rice husk ash¹⁰, pine fruit shell¹¹, deoiled soya¹², almond peel¹³, jute sticks¹⁴ and coconut fiber¹⁵.

Banana pseudo-stem which is clustered, cylindrical aggregation of leaf stalk bases¹⁶, richer in fibers, at present is a waste product of banana cultivation because each plant produce only one bunch of bananas, after its harvesting the bare pseudo-stems are cut and usually left in the soil plantation to be used as organic materials¹⁷. Banana fiber, a ligno-cellulose fiber obtained from the pseudo-stem of banana plant, is a bast fiber with relatively good mechanical properties¹⁸. This could be a new source of ligno-cellulosic fibers rich in lignin, hemicellulose and cellulose and are used for various applications, depending on their composition and physical properties such as for paper making and composite materials^{19,20}.

Brilliant green (BG) is a basic dye and exists as cation in aqueous solution (Fig. 1). BG dye is used as topical antiseptic agent and biological stain. It is also extensively used in textile dyeing and paper printing. Ingestion of BG dye causes irritation to the gastrointestinal tract with symptoms of nausea, vomiting and diarrhoea. If inhaled, causes

Fig. 1. Cationic structure of brilliant green dye.

irritation to respiratory tract and skin contact may cause irritation with redness and pain.

The aim of present study is to use fibers from the outer bark of banana pseudo-stem (BPF) as an adsorbent material for the removal of BG dye from aqueous solution.

Results and discussion

Characterization of adsorbent :

Infrared spectrum of BPF gave the information about the functional groups present in the fibers. Identification of characteristics peaks is based on previous studies of fibers. Fig. 2 shows that the adsorption at 3427 cm^{-1} is due to stretching of hydroxyl groups of cellulose, hemi-

celluloses and lignin that are present in BPF²¹. The band at 2924 cm^{-1} is due to the C-H stretching of saturated carbon. The band at 1613 cm^{-1} is due to C=C stretching of fibers containing lignin²². The band at 1363 and 1247 cm^{-1} are assigned to O-H bending and C-O stretching, respectively. The band at 1318 and 1156 cm^{-1} are due to C-C and C-O stretching, respectively²¹. The bands at 1105 and 1024 cm^{-1} are assigned to C-O-H and C-O-C stretching, respectively²³.

The morphology of fibers could provide vital information on the adsorption between the adsorbent and adsorbate. SEM micrograph (Fig. 3) shows rough texture of fibers which indicate that surface is ideal for adsorption.

The XRD spectrum of BPF shows (Fig. 4) that the fibers are partially crystalline as seen by three diffraction peaks at 13° , 22° and 28° on 2θ scale²⁴.

Effect of pH :

The efficiency of adsorption is dependent on pH of the solution because variation in pH leads to change in degree of ionization and surface charge of the adsorbent²⁵ and extent of dissociation of the active sites of adsorbent. The natural pH of stock solution (1000 mg/L) of brilliant green dye was 3.24. In this study, the pH of the dye solution was varied from 3 to 8 for 10 mg L^{-1} of initial

Fig. 2. Infrared spectrum of banana pseudo-stem fibers.

Fig. 3. SEM micrograph of banana pseudo-stem fibers.

Fig. 4. XRD spectrum of banana pseudo-stem fibers.

dye concentration. Fig. 5 shows that the percentage removal increases from 63 to 90.5% as the pH increases from 3 to 8. The pH higher than 8 was not used because of the change in dye colour and its structural characteristics. The interaction between the dye molecules and adsorbent is basically a combined result of charges on dye molecules and the surface of adsorbent. However at basic medium (pH > 7) the adsorbent has a negative charge on its functional groups and favours the adsorption of cationic dyes.

Effect of adsorbent dose :

Fig. 6 shows that the adsorption increases as the adsorbent dose increases. Initially, the increase in adsorption was very rapid from 0.2 to 1 g/L. This is because at higher dose of the adsorbent, more adsorption sites are available causing higher removal of BG. Above 1 g/L of adsorbent dose, the adsorption decreases. This was due to the fact that as the dosage of adsorbent was increased, there was less commensurate increase in adsorption resulting from the lower adsorptive capacity utilization of the adsorbent²⁶. Above the 1.2 g/L removal becomes almost constant as the surface BG concentration and the solution BG concentration come to equilibrium with each other.

Effect of stirring speed :

Stirring speed variation plays an important role in determining the efficiency of adsorption because it influences the distribution of the solute in the bulk solution and formation of external boundary film²⁷. Increase in stirring speed increases the rate of adsorption and the adsorption capacity of the adsorbent. Fig. 7 indicates that with increasing stirring speed from 50 to 600 rpm, the percentage removal of the dye increases from 88 to 91.8 during 5 min operation. This effect can be attributed to

Fig. 5. Effect of pH on removal of BG by BPF.

Fig. 6. Effect of adsorbent dose on removal of BG by BPF.

Fig. 7. Effect of stirring speed on removal of BG by BPF.

decrease in boundary film surrounding the particles thus increasing the external film transfer coefficient and hence the dye percent removal. Since the uptake of BG was not significantly enhanced by the degree of stirring after 200 rpm, therefore a stirring speed of 200 rpm was used for all further experiments.

Effect of contact time and initial dye concentration :

The effect of contact time and initial dye concentration on the adsorption of dye was investigated and shown in Fig. 8. It was observed that maximum removal occurs within 5 min and thereafter no change was observed which established that the system has reached the equilibrium point. This indicates that the rate of reaction is very fast. On increasing the initial dye concentration from 10 to 50 mg/L, percentage removal decreases from 90.5 to 86.8%. This shows that at higher concentration there will be an increased competition for the active adsorption sites which results in slowing down of adsorption. This explains the lower adsorption rate for higher concentration.

Kinetics of adsorption :

The rate constants for adsorption of BG on BPF were obtained using the Lagergren's pseudo-first order²⁸ and Ho's pseudo-second order kinetic models²⁹. The intra-particle diffusion model was also considered.

Pseudo-first order kinetic model :

When the adsorption is preceded by diffusion through a boundary, the kinetics in most cases follow the pseudo-first order rate equation. The differential rate equation is of the form :

$$dq_t/dt = k_1 (q_e - q_t) \quad (1)$$

where q_t and q_e are the amount of BG dye adsorbed at time t (mg/g) and at equilibrium (mg/g), respectively and k_1 is the pseudo-first order rate constant (min^{-1}). Integrating the above equation using the boundary condition, $q_t = 0$ at $t = 0$ leads to :

$$\log (q_e - q_t) = \log q_e - (k_1/2.303) t \quad (2)$$

The values of k_1 and q_e were calculated from the slopes and intercepts of the linear plots of $\log (q_e - q_t)$ vs t (Table 1). There is a great disagreement between experimental and calculated values of q_e as shown in Table 1. Therefore, it may be concluded that the adsorption of BG on BPF does not follow the pseudo-first order kinetic model.

Pseudo-second order kinetic model :

The pseudo-second order kinetic model is presented as :

$$dq_t/dt = k_2 (q_e - q_t)^2 \quad (3)$$

Fig. 8. Effect of contact time and initial dye concentration on removal of BG by BPF.

Table 1. Pseudo-first order, pseudo-second order kinetic and intra-particle diffusion models for adsorption of BG on BPF

Initial BG concentration (mg/L)	$q_{e, exp}$ (mg/g)	Pseudo-first order			Pseudo-second order			Intra-particle order		
		$q_{e, cal}$	k_1	R^2	$q_{e, cal}$	k_2	R^2	k_i	I	R^2
10	9.05	6.53	0.641	0.96	9.345	0.293	0.99	2.44	3.562	0.97
20	17.8	5.827	0.374	0.98	16.66	0.261	0.99	2.95	10.85	0.99
30	26.55	9.627	0.392	0.99	27.02	0.152	0.99	4.86	15.23	0.99
40	39.92	15.79	0.174	0.99	38.46	0.067	0.96	9.30	15.91	0.92
50	43.4	16.67	0.359	0.98	47.61	0.055	0.97	8.63	23.05	0.99

where q_t and q_e are the amount of dye adsorbed at time t (mg/g) and at equilibrium (mg/g), respectively and k_2 is the pseudo-second order rate constant (g/mg/min). Integrating the above equation using the boundary condition, $q_e = 0$ at $t = 0$ leads to :

$$t/q_t = 1/k_2 q_e^2 + t/q_e \quad (4)$$

The values of k_2 and q_e were calculated from the intercepts and slopes of the linear plots of t/q_t vs t (Fig. 9), respectively (Table 1). Table 1 shows that the calculated q_e values are very close to that of experimentally obtained q_e and the values of correlation coefficients (R^2) are closer to unity which confirms that adsorption of BG on BPF follows pseudo-second order kinetics.

Intra-particle diffusion model :

Adsorption is multistep process involving the transfer of solute from bulk of solution to surface of adsorbent.

Intra-particle diffusion plays an important role in the extent of adsorption with time at different initial concentrations. The intra-particle diffusion model³⁰ is given as :

$$q_t = k_i t^{0.5} + I \quad (5)$$

where q_t is the amount of dye adsorbed at time t (mg/g) and k_i is intra-particle diffusion rate constant (mg/g/min^{0.5}).

The values of k_i and I were obtained from the slopes (k_i) and intercepts, (I) of the plots of q_t vs $t^{0.5}$ (Fig. 10), respectively (Table 1). The values of I give an idea about the thickness of boundary layer i.e. the larger the intercept the greater the boundary layer effect³¹. Fig. 10 shows that the slope increases slowly and signifies that firstly the dye molecules are transported from surface of fibers through film diffusion at slow rate and thereafter the molecules enter into the fibers through pore diffusion or intra-particle diffusion. All the lines follow the same pat-

Fig. 9. Pseudo-second order kinetic model for the adsorption of BG on BPF.

Fig. 10. Intra-particle diffusion model for the adsorption of BG on BPF.

tern and do not pass through the origin and thus it can be concluded that film diffusion and intra-particle diffusion, both occur simultaneously. It seems that as the concentration of solution increases, linearity of the plot is lost because intra-particle diffusion occurs at a faster rate than

film diffusion.

Adsorption isotherms :

Equilibrium data commonly known as adsorption isotherms, describe how adsorbates interacts with adsorbents.

There are several isotherm equations available for analysis of adsorption equilibrium parameters. However, the most common types of isotherms are Langmuir [eq. (6)] and Freundlich [eq. (7)] models. The Langmuir isotherm model is applicable to monolayer adsorption while Freundlich isotherm model is used to describe adsorption on surface having heterogeneous energy distribution.

$$\text{Langmuir isotherm : } C_e/q_e = (1/bq_{\max}) + (1/q_{\max}) C_e \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Freundlich isotherm : } \ln q_e = \ln K_F + (1/n) \ln C_e \quad (7)$$

where C_e is concentration of dye solution at equilibrium (mg/L), q_e is the amount of dye adsorbed at equilibrium in unit mass of adsorbent (mg/g), q_{\max} and b are the Langmuir coefficient related to adsorption capacity (mg/g) and adsorption energy (L/mg), respectively. K_F and n are the Freundlich coefficient related to adsorption capacity [$\text{mg g}^{-1} (\text{mg L}^{-1})^{-1/n}$] and adsorption intensity of adsorbent, respectively.

The Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm models were carried out at different temperatures (303, 313 and 323 K). The Langmuir isotherm parameters q_{\max} and b were

determined from the slopes ($1/q_{\max}$) and intercepts ($1/bq_{\max}$) of the plots of C_e/q_e vs C_e (Fig. 11). The plots give straight lines, indicating that the adsorption of BG on BPF follows the Langmuir isotherm. The values of Freundlich constants n and K_F were obtained from the slopes ($1/n$) and intercepts ($\ln K_F$) of the plots of $\ln q_e$ vs $\ln C_e$ (Fig. 12). The plots give straight lines and this show that the adsorption of BG on BPF also follows the Freundlich isotherm. The values of $1/n$ are less than unity (0.81 to 0.86) indicate favourable adsorption at all temperatures. The Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms constants and regression coefficients are listed in Table 2.

Effect of temperature and thermodynamic parameters :

To observe the effect of temperature on the adsorption process, experiments were carried for different initial dye concentrations (10, 20, 30, 40 and 50 mg/L) at different temperatures (303, 313 and 323 K) using 1 g/L of adsorbent. From Fig. 13 it has been observed that the adsorption increases with increase in temperature. This implies that for each concentration, adsorption process is endothermic in nature.

The thermodynamic parameters such as change in Gibb's free energy (ΔG°), enthalpy (ΔH°) and entropy

Fig. 11. Langmuir model for the adsorption of BG on BPF.

Fig. 12. Freundlich model for the adsorption of BG on BPF.

Table 2. Langmuir and Freundlich adsorption isotherm constants for the adsorption of BG on BPF at different temperatures

Temp. (K)	Langmuir constants			Freundlich constants		
	q_{max}	b	R^2	K_F	n	R^2
303	125.0	0.080	0.962	9.46	1.23	0.999
313	142.8	0.074	0.986	10.04	1.20	0.999
323	166.6	0.071	0.991	11.02	1.16	0.999

(ΔS°) were obtained from the eqs. (8) and (9) :

$$\ln (q_e m / C_e) = \Delta S^\circ / R + -\Delta H^\circ / RT \quad (8)$$

$$\Delta G^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T\Delta S^\circ \quad (9)$$

where m is the adsorbent dose (g/L), C_e is the concentration of dye solution at equilibrium (mg/L), q_e is the amount of dye at equilibrium in unit mass of adsorbent (mg/g), q_e / C_e is called the adsorption affinity. ΔH° , ΔS° and ΔG° are change in enthalpy (J/mol), entropy (J/mol/K) and Gibb's free energy (J/mol), respectively, R is the gas constant (8.314 J/mol/K) and T is the temperature (K). If unit mass (1.0 g/L) of adsorbent dose is used, eq. (8) can be written as :

$$\ln (q_e / C_e) = \Delta S^\circ / R + -\Delta H^\circ / RT \quad (10)$$

Values of ΔH° and ΔS° were obtained from the Van't Hoff plots of $\ln (q_e / C_e)$ vs $1/T$. Once the values of ΔH° and ΔS° were obtained from the slopes ($-\Delta H^\circ / R$) and intercepts ($\Delta S^\circ / R$) of the plots, ΔG° values were determined from the eq. (9). The values of thermodynamic parameters are given in Table 3. The negative values of ΔG° show that the process is feasible and spontaneous in nature. The positive values of ΔH° show that the adsorption process is endothermic in nature. The values of ΔH° in the range of 6.3–10.6 kJ/mol (< 40 kJ/mol) indicate that the adsorption is physical in nature and existence of weak bonding between the BG and the BPF. The positive ΔS° values reflect the increase in randomness at solid/solution interface. The increase in adsorption with temperature may be attributed to increase in the mobility of the dye molecule with an increase in their kinetic energy and intra-particle diffusion with rise of temperature.

Experimental

Adsorbent :

Rolled banana leaves of pseudo-stem were chopped into cubes of average size of 2×2 cm. The cubes were

Fig. 13. Effect of temperature on removal of BG by BPF.

Table 3. Thermodynamic parameters for the adsorption of BG on BPF at different temperatures

Initial BG (mg/L)	ΔH° (kJ/mol)	ΔS° (J/mol/K)	ΔG° (kJ/mol)		
			303 K	313 K	323 K
10	6.381	39.72	-5.654	-6.051	-6.448
20	9.744	49.49	-5.251	-5.746	-6.241
30	9.211	47.26	-5.108	-5.581	-6.053
40	10.683	51.26	-4.848	-5.361	-5.873
50	10.616	50.56	-4.703	-5.209	-5.714

boiled in double distilled water for 45 min and then dried in an oven at 80 °C until a constant weight was obtained. The resulted material was ground with commercial grinder and sieved to isolate fibers of size 200–300 μ . The powder was preserved as an adsorbent in glass bottle.

Characterization of adsorbent :

FT-IR spectra were recorded on spectrophotometer (ABB-FTLA 2000) using potassium bromide (KBr) pellets. The morphology of BPF was investigated by FEI Quanta 200 scanning electron microscope operated at 20 KV accelerating voltage. For determining the crystallinity of material XRD was performed on Rigaku D/max-

2200 PC diffractometer operated at 40 KV/40 mA, using $\text{CuK}_{\alpha 1}$ radiation with wavelength of 1.54 Å in the wide angle region from 10° to 80° on 2 θ scale.

Adsorbate :

BG dye (C.I. : 42040, Basic Green 1, FW : 462.65) obtained from the Merck, was used without further purification. A stock solution of dye (1000 mg/L) was prepared by dissolving an accurately weighed quantity (1 g) of BG dye in double distilled water. The experimental solutions of desired concentration were obtained by diluting the stock solution.

Adsorption experiments :

To study the effect of important parameters like pH, adsorbent dose, stirring speed, initial dye concentration, contact time and temperature on the adsorptive removal of BG, the experiments were carried out in 150 mL of conical flasks by mixing a pre-weighed amount of the BPF with 50 mL of the aqueous dye solution of particular concentration. The mixture was agitated on stirrer at constant pH, temperature, stirring speed and contact time.

The effect of pH was studied over the pH range of 3 to 8 which was adjusted by adding 0.1 M HCl or 0.1 M NaOH. For the optimum amount of adsorbent per unit mass of adsorbate, a 50 mL of dye solution was contacted with different amounts of BPF (0.2 to 1.4 g/L) till equilibrium was attained. The effect of stirring speed on adsorption was studied at 50, 200, 400 and 600 rpm. The kinetics of adsorption was determined by analyzing the removal of dye by adsorbent from the aqueous solution at different time intervals. Adsorption isotherm was studied by agitation of different initial concentration of dye with known amount of adsorbent till equilibrium was attained. The effect of temperature on the adsorption process was investigated at 303, 313 and 323 K for different initial dye concentrations. The dye remaining unadsorbed was determined spectrophotometrically (Systronics 2203). The amount of BG adsorbed on BPF was calculated by the mass balance relationship :

$$q_e = (C_0 - C_e)V/W \quad (11)$$

where q_e is quantity of dye adsorbed on the adsorbent at the time of equilibrium (mg/g), C_0 is the initial dye concentration (mg/L), C_e is the concentration of dye at equilibrium (mg/L), V is the volume of solution (L) and W is the mass of fibers (g).

Conclusions :

This study shows that the BPF is an effective adsorbent for removal of BG dye from aqueous solution. 1 g/L of adsorbent dose was able to remove about 90% of BG dye within 5 min at 303 K. The adsorption was pH dependent. The rate of adsorption followed pseudo-second order kinetic model and intra-particle diffusion model. The adsorption of BG dye onto the BPF follows both, Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm models. The negative values of ΔG° indicate the adsorption process was spontaneous. The positive values of ΔH° and ΔS° show the endothermic nature of process and increased randomness, respectively.

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